

Oracle R technologies for data analytics and machine learning in hybrid data systems

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Project Specification

The goal of this Openlab summer student project is to evaluate Oracle R Advanced Analytics for Hadoop (ORAAH) as a platform for CERN Big Data Analytics. It provides R interface to manipulate the data stored in HDFS, relational databases and file systems along with leveraging the capabilities of CRAN R packages. ORAAH also uses both HIVE transparency capabilities and maps HDFS as direct input into Machine Learning algorithms that can run as Map Reduce jobs or inside an Apache Spark container. The objective was to determine if the Cryogenic Valve Degradation analyses and Automatic Detection of Faulty valve can be efficiently done, in terms of CPU usage and time for completion of the job using ORAAH and Apache Spark. ORAAH allows you to run your R queries on Hadoop against data in HDFS, giving you the benefits of using R while taking advantage of the horizontal scalability of Hadoop and MapReduce. ORAAH is designed for parallel reads and writes, has resource management and database connectivity features, so it can be used together with ORE. Apart from this, the components like ORAAH Spark MLLib algorithms make the analysis, classification and prediction problems easier.

Software Specifications:

- BigDataLite VM 4.5.0
- Oracle R Advanced Analytics for Hadoop 2.6.0
 - ORCH package
 - Interaction with HDFS
 - Map-Reduce Jobs
 - Orch.ml.svm (Spark MLLib container for Support Vector Machine Algorithm)
- Apache Spark 1.6.0
 - Spark SQL
 - com.databricks:spark-csv_2.10:1.4.0
 - Spark MLLib
 - org.apache.spark.mllib.classification{SVMMModel,SVMWithSGD}
 - org.apache.spark.mllib.evaluation.BinaryClassificationMetrics
 - org.apache.spark.mllib.util.MLUtils
- R 3.3.0
 - caret
 - rpart
 - e1071
 - ggplot2
 - reshape

Abstract

I present an evaluation of Oracle R Advanced Analytics for Hadoop as a Big Data Analysis platform for advance analytics and machine learning. I have used R as a basic modelling tool as it one of the most powerful statistical and computing languages with a number of predefined functionalities available to allow an easy analysis and testing of data. To provide a comparison and truly judge the performance of ORAAH, Apache Spark has been used to model the same approaches. The performance has been measured on the basis of the time consumed to build the model and the accuracy of the model.

The task in this project was aimed to study the potential applicability of the aforementioned technologies using real CERN analytics use cases: (a) The degradation analysis of cryogenic valves in LHCb (b) Predict faulty cryogenic valves.

The above mentioned use cases were duly run and modelled using the technologies mentioned earlier and the results computed provided very promising statistics for future use of scalable services as CERN Big Data Analytics platform.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction
2. Goals
3. Use Case 1: Cryogenic Valves Degradation Analysis
 - 3.1 Data set.....
 - 3.2 Data frame.....
 - 3.3 Procedure.....
 - 3.3.1 Working in R.....
 - 3.3.2 Working in ORAAH.....
 - 3.3.3 Working in Spark SQL.....
4. Use Case 2: Pattern Classification for Faulty Cryo Valves
 - 4.1 Data set.....
 - 4.2 Data frame.....
 - 4.3 Procedure.....
 - 4.3.1 Transforming data to classification problem
 - 4.3.2 Machine Learning.....
 - 4.3.3 Performance Metrics.....
 - 4.3.4 Dividing data into training and testing.....
 - 4.4 Implementation on Scalable Platform...
 - 4.4.1 ORAAH (Oracle R Advanced Analytics for Hadoop)
 - 4.4.2 Spark MLlib Algorithm.....
 - 4.4.3 ROC Curve.....
 - 4.4.4 Comparision.....
5. Improving ORAAH
6. Conclusion
7. Reference

1 Introduction

In this I present the evaluation of ORAAH, the Oracle R Advanced Analytics for Hadoop, for large data sets and advanced analytics at scalable platform. Oracle R Advanced Analytics for Hadoop (ORAAH) allows you to run your R queries on Hadoop against data in HDFS, giving you the benefits of using R while taking advantage of the horizontal scalability of Hadoop and MapReduce. ORAAH is designed for parallel reads and writes, has resource management and database connectivity features. At its core, ORAAH provides an R interface for manipulating data stored in HDFS, using both HIVE transparency capabilities and mapping HDFS as direct input into Machine Learning algorithms that can run as Map Reduce jobs or inside an Apache Spark container.

CERN has a number of data analysis use cases which deal with heavy volume, high velocity and wide variety of data. The diversity of data analysis requirement has been increasing at a very rapid rate. But thankfully, we have a number of new scalable services emerging which would prove perfect for the data analytics requirement at CERN. ORAAH, is one such service by oracle which will be very useful for CERN's use cases. It encourages the user to build models on Hadoop platform to speed up the production process.

The entire evaluation work was driven by real analytics use cases for the cryogenic installation, which represent the state-of-art of the field. My work was to study these use cases, the applicability of ORAAH and Spark and test their efficiency and potential benefits. Working with Spark and ORAAH is efficient, faster and more accurate than non-scalable services. The results obtained would be helpful to drive guidelines on analytics for further development.

2 GOALS

- Prepare the ORAAH environment on Cloudera VM CDH 5.7.1
- For use case 1, prepare the data frame in R. Initial modeling is done in R.
 - Preprocess the data in HIVE for ORAAH.
 - Feed to HDFS and then run Map Reduce
 - Perform the same analysis in Apache Spark using Spark SQL
- Evaluate the efficiency of both the platforms for Degradation Analysis Use case.
- For Use case 2, prepare the data frame in R for preprocessing.
 - Preprocess the data in R and feed it to SVM and Mahalanobis distance and compare their efficiency.
 - Take the better model and use it on the scalable platform.
 - Perform Analysis in ORAAH
 - Perform Analysis in Spark
 - Compare Efficiency.
- Plot graphs and evaluate System Time.

3: Use Case 1 - Cryogenic Valves Degradation Analysis

CERN has one of the largest cryogenic installations facilitating the activities of the collider. Being mechanical components they tend to wear out after a certain period of time and their efficiency decreases. After an extensive study on the working of these valves it was found out that there was a difference between the order which an operator provides the valves and the feedback which they receive from the valve. The work here is focused on analyzing this error over the course of many years to get to the root of it.

The traditional workflow was carried out in a non-scalable platform where the issue of distributed processing arised. Hence, I present my work on two scalable platforms, namely Apache Spark and ORAAH.

3.1 Dataset

The data is in the time-series format containing records for over 4 years. The data set contains the data from QSCB_6_2CV120 for this particular analysis. Though the data can be taken from many of the valves for analysis, we choose one.

The process can be defined by 3 distinct parts /Timestamp/ Type of value (Variable Name)/ Value from the valve

Timestamp	Variable_name (QSCB_6_2CV120 valve name)	Value (amount of valve is open)
2014-12-02 08:44:34.17	QSCB_6_2CV120.POSRST (order to the valve)	93.8
2014-12-02 08:44:37.21	QSCB_6_2CV120.POSRST(feedback from the valve)	85.4

Table 1: The structure of dataset for degradation analysis

3.2 Data Frame

Data frame is the input file in comma separated values format. This is the file on which the machine learning algorithms are run upon. It contains many datasets, and each dataset is uniquely represented by one row in the data frame.

For my application, I modeled the problem in R, Spark SQL and ORAAH.

- **R:** the data frame was an R object taking data directly from the data file
- **Spark SQL:** Initially the data is taken from CSV file and fed into the analysis problem in form of HDFS files.

- **ORAAH:** The data first fed into HDFS, manipulated by HIVE (grouped and pivoted) and then the HIVE tables are used by ORAAH in the R environment.

3.3 Procedure

3.3.1 Working in R

Taking the reference of the MATLAB code from traditional workflow, the degradation analysis of the cryogenic valves in the LHCb ring in CERN has been implemented on a non-scalable platform in R. The analysis deals with calculating the difference between the order given by an operator to the valves (QSCB_6_2CV120.POSST) and the feedback from the valves (QSCB_6_2CV120.POSRST) at a particular timestamp.

- Changed the timestamp in POSIXct
- Check iteratively for an order value, if it's there check for the very next feedback value. Calculate the error (order- feedback), note the timestamp, and map the timestamp and error to x and y axis accordingly.

Being a non-scalable platform, it did not provide much efficiency. It involved the process of extracting and moving the data to be processed at a local source which is expensive. The local processing on a single machine was not powerful enough and it consumed a lot of time. It was difficult to process it in a distributed manner.

Execution Time: Approximately 2.5 hours

Result:

Fig 1: Graph showing variation between the error and time period ranging for years

3.3.2 Working in ORAAH (Oracle R Advanced Analytics for Hadoop)

Having issues with the non-scalable platform, we switched to the scalable solutions. Here I present my work with ORAAH for handling the problem of Degradation Analysis.

- Initially the data is being pre-processed in HIVE.
- A hive table has been created
- Grouped by timestamp
- Pivot by variable name (QSCB_6_2CV120.POSRST/
QSCB_6_2CV120.POSST)

Timestamp	QSCB_6_2CV120.POSRST	QSCB_6_2CV120.POSST
2014-12-02 08:44:34.17	93.8	85.4
2014-12-02 08:44:37.21	96.8	87.7
2016-01-18 08:12:17.9	20.056	20.49

Table 3: Resultant Structure of Data

- The data is stored back into the Hive table which is then extracted into ORAAH R environment.
- The error is calculated through a Map-Reduce process.

Execution Time: Approximately 648.97 seconds

Fig 2: The resultant error analysis in ORAAH

3.3.3 Working in Spark SQL

Apache Spark is an open source cluster computing framework which provides an interface for programming entire clusters with implicit data parallelism and fault-tolerance. Spark SQL is a component on top of Spark Core that introduces a new data abstraction called DataFrames, which provides support for structured and semi-structured data. Spark SQL provides a domain-specific language to manipulate Data Frames in Scala, Java, or Python. It also provides SQL language support.

- I used **com.databricks:spark-csv_2.10:1.4.0^[1]** package for reading from the csv files and also for manipulating the data structure.
- Using SQL Context, I dealt with the analysis of the time series data.
- Firstly, I stored the data in HDFS and read the data in databricks format.
- The data was then **grouped by timestamp, pivoted by variable name, and averaged by value.**
- **The resultant data frame is:**

Timestamp	QSCB_6_2CV120.POSRST	QSCB_6_2CV120.POSST
2014-12-02 08:44:34.17	93.8	85.4
2014-12-02 08:44:37.21	96.8	87.7
2016-01-18 08:12:17.9	20.056	20.49

Table 4: Data frame for Spark SQL implementation

- After calculating the error, the data frame :

Timestamp	QSCB_6_2CV120.POSRST	QSCB_6_2CV120.POSST	Error
2014-12-02 08:44:34.17	93.8	85.4	8.4
2014-12-02 08:44:37.21	96.8	87.7	9.1
2016-01-18 08:12:17.9	20.056	20.49	-0.434

Table 5: The final result after pre-processing and error analysis

- The results are plotted accordingly in the form of a graph.

Execution Time: 164.33 seconds

4 Use Case 2: Pattern Classification for Faulty Cryo Valves

The aim of this procedure was to detect automatically if the behaviour of a valve is normal or if it is faulty based on Pattern Classification techniques. Having to know that there has been degradation in the cryogenic systems, it is more than likely to that some valves are faulty. So there arises a need to have an intelligent system which could classify, efficiently, if the valves are faulty or not. The data from a number of valves are taken, pre-processed and fed into the classifiers to get best results. The platform used to analyse the data is scalable to address the need of distributed processing.

4.1 Data Set

A set of examples of non-faulty valves is selected by visual inspection and used as a learning set. For each valve, the aperture order (in %) and the aperture measured (in %) are recorded every second during 24 hours where a least one current cycle was done. The signal used is the difference between the aperture order and the aperture measured, named S.

The data is from three valves **CV910/CV943/CV947**.

Read_id(id of each cycle)	Cycle_id	Valve (valve number CV910/CV943/CV947)	Aperture_order (order to the valve)	Aperture_measure (feedback from valve)	Status (1 for faulty and 0 for Normal)
1	1	910	20.1	21.7	1
2	1	910	20	21.7	1

Table 6: Data frame for Pattern Classification Problem

Size of Data set: 413.4 MB

4.2 Data Frame

Data frame is the input file in comma separated values format. This is the file on which the machine learning algorithms are run upon. It contains many datasets, and each dataset is uniquely represented by one row in the data frame.

For my application, I modeled the problem in R, Spark SQL and ORAAH.

- **R** : The initial pre-processing and modeling (Mahalanobis distance, SVM) is done in R where the data was in the form of a data frame class in R after being extracted from CSV.
- **ORAAH**: the data fed into the training and testing for this platform is in the form of HDFS files.
- **Spark** : The per processed data is in the form of CSV file. This data is then converted to LIBSVM format using a python script. The resultant is then fed into HDFS where it is then extracted as HDFS files for processing.

4.3 Procedure

4.3.1 Transforming data to classification problem – Pre Processing

The error (aperture_order – aperture_measure) = S is calculate for each id and finally the features for modelling are computed in the following manner, per cycle.

For each valve of the training set, two sets of features are selected. The first one is composed of:

- the signal X variance : $\text{Var}(S)$
- the maximal value of S : $\text{Max}(S)$
- the noise band B(S): it is calculated from the power spectrum of the signal. Let Pxx be the power spectrum of the signal S, from 0 to 0.5Hz, where S has been previously mean-centered.

$$B(S) = \frac{\left| \sum_{k=1}^{N_{fft}/2} P_{xx}(k) \right|^2}{\sum_{k=1}^{N_{fft}/2} P_{xx}(k)^2}$$

- the “rope” distance of S. It is the length of the rope when it is tied to the beginning of the signal S, placed on every sampling value until the end of the signal. It is calculated by :

$$R(S) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=2}^N |S(i) - S(i-1)|$$

Each signal from the original dataset, S_i , is set is then summarized by a vector $X_i = [Var(S_i) \quad Max(S_i) \quad B(S_i) \quad R(S_i)]$

The learning set is the matrix $X_L = \begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ X_i \\ X_N \end{bmatrix}$.

4.3.2 Applying Machine Learning

Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence which is concerned with the construction and study of systems that are able to learn from data. Hence, basically it is a type of artificial intelligence that provides computers with the ability to learn without being explicitly programmed. Machine learning focuses on the development of computer programs that can teach themselves to grow and change when exposed to new data.

Types of Machine Learning:

- **Supervised Learning:** Supervised learning methods provide labels in the training data set and the computer has to learn from these examples.
- **Unsupervised Learning:** Learning happens automatically and the structures hidden in the data are automatically recognized by the system.
- **Semi-Supervised Learning:** This is not based on any major distinction, but it actually depends on the type and size of the data. Semi-supervised learning is a class of supervised learning tasks and techniques that also make use of unlabeled data for training.

For initial modeling, I used two of the classifiers to compare the accuracy obtained by both and pick the most accurate one for analysis on a scalable platform.

Mahalanobis Distance:

The mean of X_L (M_L) and the covariance matrix of X_L (C_L) was calculated.

$$M_L = \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N Var(S_i) \quad \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N Max(S_i) \quad \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N B(S_i) \quad \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N R(S_i) \right]$$

$$C_L = \frac{1}{N-1} (X_L - M_L)^T (X_L - M_L)$$

For each example of the training set, the Mahalanobis distance of the example to the mean value of the training set was calculated :

$$DM(X_i) = (X_i - M_L) * inv(C_L) * (X_i - M_L)^T$$

The learning set is used to fix detection thresholds. The detection can be univariate : whenever one of the features exceeds the detection threshold, the valve is faulty. It can be multivariate : whenever the Mahalanobis distance of the example to the mean value of the training set exceeds a threshold, the valve is faulty. The detection is multivariate because the Mahalanobis distance is calculated using all the features.

For each variable, the detection threshold is fixed as the mean value of the variable plus alpha times the standard deviation.

$Th_V = M_V + \alpha * S_V$ with M_V , S_V the mean value and the standard deviation estimated from the learning set. Alpha was set to 5.

Detection :

To make a diagnosis on a new valve :

- Get the aperture order (in %) and the aperture measured (in %) recorded every second during 24 hours where a least one current cycle was done. Calculate the difference between the aperture order and the aperture measured, named S_{new} .
- Extract the feature on S_{new} :

$$X_{new} = [Var(S_{new}) \quad Max(S_{new}) \quad B(S_{new}) \quad R(S_{new})]$$

- Calculate the Mahalanobis distance of X_{new} to to the mean value of the training set :

$$DM(X_{new}) = (X_{new} - M_L) * inv(C_L) * (X_{new} - M_L)^T$$

- Compare the Mahalanobis distance to the detection threshold.

It is also possible to make an univariate detection. In this case, each feature of X_{new} is compared to its corresponding threshold.

The results obtained (see section below) showed that the multivariate detection is more sensitive than the monivariate ones. Whenever one on the features exceeds its threshold, the detection is also made by the multi-variate detection. On some examples, only the multi-variate detector detected a faulty valve, while the univariate detectors let it pass.

Support Vector Machine

It is a supervised learning method with associated learning algorithms that analyze data used for classification and regression analysis. Given a set of training examples, each marked for belonging to one of two categories, an SVM training algorithm builds a model that assigns new examples into one category or the other, making it a non-probabilistic binary linear classifier. In addition to performing linear classification, SVMs can efficiently perform a non-linear classification using what is called the kernel trick, implicitly mapping their inputs into high-dimensional feature spaces. A support vector machine constructs a hyperplane or set of hyperplanes in a high- or infinite-dimensional space, which can be used for classification, regression, or other tasks.

4.3.3 Performance Evaluation

After the initial modelling of the problem in R, the resultant accuracy of each classifier was obtained. These results were calculated on the training set comprising of the data from valve CV943+CV947 and the testing set comprising of CV910 data. To finalise the classifier to be used for modelling on scalable platform, the accuracy of each classifier was tested. This was done by the traditional technique of Confusion Matrix.

Confusion Matrix:

In the field of machine learning and specifically the problem of statistical classification, a confusion matrix, also known as an error matrix, is a specific table layout that allows visualization of the performance of an algorithm, typically a supervised learning one. Each column of the matrix represents the instances in a predicted class while each row represents the instances in an actual class.

		Predicted	
		Positive	Negative
Original	Positive	True Positive	False Negative
	Negative	False Positive	True Negative

Accuracy = (True Positive + True Negative) / (Total)

Evaluation Metrics (Accuracy by each classifier)

- **Mahalanobis Distance** : 0.94
- **Support Vector Machine** : 0.96

Hence, I chose Support Vector Machine for analysis on a scalable platform.

Fig 3: Schematic of initial modelling in R of the pre-processed dataset to decide the classifier

4.3.4 Dividing data into Training and Testing set

After a number of tests of which type of train and test division gives the best classification results with the best accuracy, it was decided to divide the dataset as:

Training: CV943 + CV947

Testing: CV910

4.4 Implementation on Scalable Platform

4.4.1 ORAAH (Oracle R Advanced Analytics for Hadoop)

- After the initial processing of the accuracy in R, it was found out that the Support Vector Machine when fed with the training set from CV943+CV947 and the test set from CV910, gave an accuracy 0.96
- The features like mean, variance, maximum error, Noise band and Rope Distance were calculated in R.
- These features were saved in the form of a data frame which was then directly fed to HDFS using ORCH Library

```
library(rpart)
library(ORCH)

spark.connect(master="yarn-client",memory="2G",
dfs.namenode="bigdatalite.localdomain")

train <- hdfs.put(training)
model <- orch.ml.svm(formula = status ~ rope_dist +
                    bs + mean + var + max ,data = train)

test <- hdfs.put(testing)
pred <- predict(model, newdata = test)
hdfs.write(pred, outPath = "Prediction")
```

Implementation of SVM in ORAAH

Performance Metrics

The performance metrics describe how good one algorithm is when it comes to the time for training the model and how accurate the predictions are.

System Time: Approximately 200 seconds

Confusion Matrix:

		Predicted	
		0	1
Original	0	48	0
	1	1	1

Table 7: Confusion Matrix for SVM in ORAAH

Evaluation Metrics	
Accuracy	0.98
95% CI	(0.8935, 0.9995)
No Information Rate	0.98
P-Value[Acc > NIR]	0.7358
Kappa	0.6575
Mcnemar's Test P-Value	1.000
Sensitivity	0.9796
Specificity	1.0000

Table 8: Evaluation Metrics for SVM in ORAAH

4.4.2 Spark MLlib Algorithm

- After the initial processing of the accuracy in R, it was found out that the Support Vector Machine when fed with the training set from CV943+CV947 and the test set from CV910, gave an accuracy 0.96
- The data was initially stored in data frame format and then copied as a CSV file in the file system.
- The csv file is then converted to LIBSVM format using a simple python script.
- The result is then stored in HDFS and fed into the algorithm accordingly.

```
import
org.apache.spark.mllib.classification.{SVMModel,SVMWithSGD}
import
org.apache.spark.mllib.evaluation.BinaryClassificationMetrics

import org.apache.spark.mllib.util.MLUtils
import org.apache.spark.SparkContext._

val train = MLUtils.loadLibSVMFile(sc, "/user/r1/train.data")
val test = MLUtils.loadLibSVMFile(sc, "/user/r2/test.data")

val numIterations = 90
val model = SVMWithSGD.train(train, numIterations)

model.clearThreshold()

val scoreAndLabels = test.map { point =>
  val score = model.predict(point.features)
  (score, point.label)
}

val metrics = new BinaryClassificationMetrics(scoreAndLabels)
val auROC = metrics.areaUnderROC()

println("Area under ROC = " + auROC)

model.save(sc, "/home/cloudera/d")
val sameModel = SVMModel.load(sc, "target/tmp/
  scalaSVMWithSGDModel")
```

Implementation of SVM in Spark using Apache Spark MLlib Algorithm

Performance Metrics:

Spark	ORAAH
Accuracy : 0.98	Accuracy : 0.973
System Time: 12.95 seconds	System Time: 39.537 seconds

Table 9: Overall Accuracy and System Efficiency of Spark and ORAAH

4.4.3 ROC Curve

In statistics, a receiver operating characteristic (ROC), or ROC curve, is a graphical plot that illustrates the performance of a binary classifier system as its discrimination threshold is varied. The curve is created by plotting the true positive rate (TPR) against the false positive rate (FPR) at various threshold settings. The true-positive rate is also known as sensitivity, recall or probability of detection in machine learning. The false-positive rate is also known as the fall-out or probability of false alarm.

Fig 4: ROC Curve showing the overall accuracy of implementation of SVM in ORAAH

4.4.4 Comparision

ORAAH

- Requires spark connectivity to use the orch.ml.svm() container for modeling Support Vector Machine problem
- Works on Apache Spark Mlib Algorithm container, internally, in the background
- Data from HIVE tables and from R data frames can be directly fed into HDFS from where it is used easily by the algorithm
- The structure of the data frame does not have to be manipulated as the column names can be easily used for analysis
- Easy to understand the workflow and manipulate the formulas for the algorithm
- Being more or less on R standards makes it easy for people to follow and ultimately derive best results efficiently.
- Comparatively slower than Apache Spark

SPARK

- Requires Apache Spark Mlib SVMwithSGD() library for modeling the dataset
- Requires the data to be in LIBSVM format before it can be fed into HDFS to be used by the SVMwithSGD() algorithm.
- Requires the structure of the dataset to be changed as per the requirement of the algorithm(class labels to occur first and then features)

5 Improving ORAAH

While working on the Oracle R Advanced Analytics for Hadoop platform of BigDataLite Virtual Machine, I faced two issues. These issues were then discussed with experts from Oracle on the Community Forums and some of them were solved while the others require further analysis.

- **BigDataLite VM – Ground Configuration**
 - **Error** in `.ora.get.csv.metadata(data)` : could not find function "orch.dloge"
 - **Feedback:** setting the `HIVE_HOME=/usr/lib/hive` in `/usr/lib64/R/etc/Renviron.site`
- **Orch package – sampling error**
 - **Error:** Object too large for sampling
 - **Feedback :** The error message is incorrect

6 Conclusion

Oracle R Advanced Analytics for Hadoop provides a very promising and sophisticated platform for the analysis of data for an environment like that of CERN. ORAAH provides better scalability, higher performance, a user friendly interface along with leveraging a number of CRAN R packages. The functionalities of ORAAH including Apache Saprk MLib containers, HIVE transparency capabilities and ease in usage of R functions makes a very well managed scalable analysis possible. Therefore ORAAH can be considered without a doubt a data analysis platform for CERN real time use cases.

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